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ANTI-DISCRIMINATION EDUCATIONAL PROGRAM AGAINST LABOR MIGRATION: CASE OF RURAL SCHOOL

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У статті окреслено причини трудової міграції сільського працездатного населення до міста та її наслідки як персонально для людей, так і для села як громади. Проаналізовано зв'язок між міграцією і шкільною освітою. Вивчено один із шляхів попередження міграції – створення недискримінаційного середовища школи. На прикладі Огіївського навчально-виховного комплексу визначено роль сучасного педагога, який навчається протягом життя, зокрема в процесі створення недискримінаційного простору закладу освіти як простору рівних можливостей. На прикладі діяльності антидискримінаційного центру Огіївського навчально-виховного комплексу визначено конкретні напрями і шляхи надання інформаційно-методичної та практичної підтримки з проведення антидискримінаційної експертизи шкільних підручників, гендерного аналізу уроків, зміни візуального простору на гендерночутливий, проведення уроків та виховних заходів без транслювання гендерних стереотипів, проведення гендерного аудиту закладу освіти.

Показано як участь у дослідно-експериментальній роботі регіонального рівня «Науково-методичні заходи впровадження гендерних підходів в систему роботи закладів освіти на 2014 – 2018 роки» сприяла розкриттю творчого потенціалу учасників і учасниць, розвитку їх критичного мислення, рефлексійних здібностей та готовності до сприйняття нових ідей. Адже і педагоги, і учні на своєму позитивному досвіді усвідомили, що навчання протягом життя підвищує конкурентоздатність як окремих осіб, так і закладу освіти в цілому, формує демократичні цінності. Показано, що наступним кроком ефективної діяльності закладу стало створення екологічного проєкту «Збирай роздільно сміття – буде щасливим життя», який поширився на всю громаду. Отже завдяки натхненній і орієнтованій на сучасні тенденції роботі навчального закладу змінюється свідомість місцевого населення, яке розуміє, що жити в недискримінаційному та екологічно чистому середовищі набагато комфортніше. Проаналізовано показники кількості працездатного населення села за останні роки

Ключові слова: трудова міграція, сільська школа, недискримінаційне освітнє середовище, навчання впродовж життя

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1. Introduction

Over the last century, urban trends have been one of the most pronounced in Ukraine, and now they appear inevitable. If according to the census of the Ukrainian SSR in 1926, the share of urban population was only 19.6 % [1], then in 2019, according to the State Statistics Service of Ukraine, a similar indicator (excluding the temporarily occupied territory of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea and Sevastopol) is already 69.4 % [2], and the trend for its gradual increase is obvious: the annual increase of the urban population has recently fluctuated at the level of 0.35–0.40 % [2].

Obviously, the main reason is the internal migration from rural to urban areas, the speed of which has not decreased during the period of Ukraine's independence, but on the contrary, it has become quite threatening. According to official figures, between 1990 and 2019, the rural population decreased by 24 % (from 16969.3 million to 12896.5 million), although its share among the total population of the country decreased uncritically: from 32, % in 1990 to 30.6 % in 2019 [2]. On the other hand, according to the general statistics, the problem of real labor migration of the rural population is hidden, which, having become de facto of a huge scale, remains

not so obvious: leaving home for the sake of seasonal, rotational and longer (even permanent) jobs, residents of villages do not rush to register their new place of residence, and therefore remain "invisible" for an accurate statistical account of their stay.

An additional focus of attention on the working population "highlights" the scale of the "tectonic shift". In this way, it can be found, that the number of people aged 15–70, who are considered active in the rural population, is currently 5.6 million, of which approximately 2 million (!) are migrant workers [3] who seek to realize themselves abroad and in Ukraine in cities (above all, in the capital and regional centers), objectively comparing the labor market in rural areas (respectively, and the level of wages) with other options.

The relevance of the problem of internal labor migration of the rural population (this problem is chosen as the subject of the study, while transboundary migration is deliberately left out of focus) for modern Ukraine is explained, of course, not only by its scale on the background of other social processes, but also by a number of negative consequences. brought about by mass labor migration from the village. For example, a migrant person often faces such consequences as the loss of previous

qualifications (often these people are engaged in unskilled labor jobs in a new place or under the pressure, they are forced to acquire other professional competencies, usually related to service work); the feeling of loneliness; break of family and cultural ties (first of all, this is the actual reluctance to bring up children, and in case, when a couple migrates, leaving the older generation with a child in care, there is a phenomenon, called social orphanage; besides, in the case of labor migration, there is often a communicative break with partners and family as a whole, that can even lead to divorce). Of course, most of the problems listed are relevant not only for migrants themselves but also for their families.

Other, but also important, negative consequences of labor migration are felt by the village communities (loss of the human and economic potential, labor resources, first of all, skilled workers, break of cultural ties and some others), as well as the city where the number of rural migrants has an effect on local labor markets, real estate, social sphere and so on.

It is obvious that the problem of labor migration of rural population has to be solved comprehensively at the state level. However, some successful steps can also be taken at the local level – within a community itself, and local secondary education institutions, which traditionally have the status of "more than just a school" in villages, being some of the most respected educational and cultural centers that also employ the recognized staffing potential, and if there is a community support, they have a great motivation to implement any major social programs.

Initiated by educators, by their nature, such programs can focus only on the level of an educational institution itself and have a limited impact on the community as a whole, and they also can spread activities to the whole village and then the outcome can be expected to be much more meaningful. Of course, the second option, because of its potentially higher efficiency, is more desirable, and the experience of such an educational program is discussed in this article. In 2019, the mentioned program was designed by the teaching staff of the local educational complex and with the support of the village council in the village of Ohijivka in the Sakhnovshchyna district of the Kharkiv region, and its practical implementation is currently underway.

The problem of labor migration of the population is known to the village of Ohijivka: if in 2001 there were 915 people, then in 2019 – 857 people. Although the negative balance is only 6.8 %, which does not look too threatening against the background of the national picture, it should be noted, that the village was left by the youngest and most skilled workforce and the further prospect of village development in this context looks uncertain. Such conclusions are determined by the results of a sociological survey that was conducted among pupils of grades 9–11 of the Ohijivka Educational Complex in September 2019: all 12 (out of 15 according to the lists) present persons were interviewed on the day of the interview in a semi-standardized form.

100 % of respondents answered Yes to the question "Would you like to leave the village after leaving school?" Among the reasons for this decision, in particular, were: "I do not want to stay here", "There is nothing

to do here", "Here is the end of self-development, and I still want to try and learn a lot", "There is no work and opportunities to earn enough money", "There are more chances there, a new life ...", "There is a little opportunity for development here, insufficient conditions for keeping the family" (the wording of the respondents is saved).

The vast majority (75 %) of those surveyed claimed that the decision to leave the village was made by them on their own. Another 25 % indicated that they were driven by life itself. "We did not decide – the God commanded", one of the respondents wrote such a philosophical sentence in the questionnaire.

What plans do high school students have? Mostly, they want to go to the regional center (75 %), many of them also consider going to the capital (50 %) or another regional center (50 %). And only a third of those surveyed – and this only occupies the fourth place in our rating of choice of a future place of residence and work – seek to travel abroad (which indirectly indicates the priority of internal migration for the younger generation of the village of Ohijivka).

The last asked question was quite significant: "If in the village, there was a well-paid job and other opportunities for development and recreation, would you leave it?" The answers were different: 50 % of the respondents would still follow their previous decision, 42 % would prefer to stay, and one person (8 %) could not answer clearly.

The hypothesis, stated by the pedagogical staff of the Ohijivka Educational Complex, was the assumption that the inability to find jobs and opportunities for self-realization in the village (or at least within the district) is in fact largely related to the various stereotypes, inherent in modern youth, as well as with some discriminatory practices that influence indirectly and disseminate ideas about the secondary importance of rural areas to the city to young people. And if they could be effectively overcome (or prevented), the statistics on rural labor migration in the village of Ohijivka could be changed.

The Ohijivka Educational Complex staff have the extensive previous experience of successful anti-discrimination initiatives and projects, understanding the direct cause and effect of relationship between the stereotypes, prevailing in the public consciousness, and the choice-of-life (in particular, professional and work) trajectories. So, they have launched a comprehensive long-term program to create an anti-discrimination environment at the level of the educational institution and settlement with the purpose of overcoming negative tendencies, in particular, those of labor migration of the population of the village of Ohijivka.

The above-mentioned program is currently taking its first steps. It is assessed as a pilot, however, if successfully implemented, it can easily be extrapolated to the socio-cultural reality of any other Ukrainian village. Therefore, based on the social significance of the program, a thorough study of its content, implementation experience and results appears to be an important scientific task.

2. Literature review

It should be noted, that the phenomenon of labor migration of the rural population in different countries is

the subject of numerous researches of scientists, which specify the causes, tendencies, and consequences of such migration as a world phenomenon.

The problem is being thoroughly investigated by the University of North Carolina Population Center (UNC CPC), in particular as part of a research project on technical assistance in developing areas, especially in Latin America. In Ecuador, Guatemala, Mexico, and Indonesia they developed, coordinated and monitored household surveys on migration, fertility, economic development, poverty, land use, and the environment. Studying migration and population changes in rural areas in a global context, the projected models for rural population growth have been developed to determine the extent, to which the internal migration of developing countries is directed to rural areas, to which rural areas and to which countries people move and how it affects the environment, etc. [4].

International studies have identified migration factors, including, for example, the material level of the country, the direction of financial and transport flows, the level of education of the population and the comfort level of living conditions in the country [5, 6].

It should be noted, that some scholars see rural migration as a source of rural renewal, finding and awakening innovative development resources. Thus, by studying the impact of urban-rural migration on rural communities of South-Eastern Nigeria, the researchers identified positive trends in this phenomenon, including, in particular, financial support to rural communities through money transfers and the involvement of migrants in rural-urban development projects, etc. [7].

In Ukraine, the prevalence of often unjustified stereotypes and discriminatory practices that undermine the dignity of people from the countryside, promote the perception of limited development opportunities for self-fulfillment, and the objective socio-economic hardship of people in the countryside is urgent.

According to the results of researches of Ukrainian scientists, unfortunately, the school content, including textbooks, used by school students, was a significant source of different stereotypes. The problem of stereotypes and discriminatory concepts that prevail in the school content was so acute that in order to overcome it, in 2016, the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine introduced an anti-discrimination examination of textbook projects. It provides for the identification and elimination of all instances of discrimination that break, in particular, Article 1 of the Law of Ukraine "On the Principles of Prevention and Combating Discrimination in Ukraine". In the first year of the examination, there were none of the textbooks, submitted to the competition, that would be fully consistent with the non-discriminatory approach in education (14 % met the requirements partially and 86 % – did not meet). The examination revealed that in the Ukrainian textbooks, many children can find neither a reflection of themselves nor a reflection of their relatives nor of the circumstances, in which they live. This distortion of the minds of children by hiding the realities or imposing stereotypes runs counter to the reform policy of the New Ukrainian School, which is now being implemented in Ukraine.

The current trend is positive and last year, 22 % of textbook projects were fully non-discriminatory, 70 % partially and only 8 % were discriminatory. This year, of all 256 textbook projects for grades 2, 6 and 11, 108 (42.5 %) were completely non-discriminatory, 144 (56.7 %) partially non-discriminatory and only 2 (0.8 %) – did not meet the requirements. The progress and desire of the authors to create the best textbooks for children are obvious.

Ukraine has something to be proud of, because such an examination is a Ukrainian innovation. It all started with a UNICEF report that analyzed and proved with examples that textbook discrimination is a worldwide problem. Ukrainian experts had previously done a similar scientific analysis of Ukrainian curricula and other educational literature, so the Ministry of Education and Science decided to use their experience and launched a special examination of the textbooks.

"When we told government officials and educators from Germany, Sweden, Finland about the experience of examining textbooks before publishing, they reacted, 'Cool, we want that too. Teach us', the experts involved in the examination told. Because they have the same problem – not so many, but there are cases of discrimination in textbooks. Some people are doing this on a social basis in other countries. But we do not know about any systematic examination at the state level in any country" [8].

The Ministry of Education and Science, considering that the expertise has no analogues in the world, regards it as an innovation and emphasizes, "No discriminatory content should be included at the very initial stage of educational content creation. That is why, with the technical support of the United Nations Population Fund, training programs on how to create a non-discriminatory educational content have been organized for authors and publishers.

And the results of this training are very optimistic, they are confirmed by quantitative and qualitative indicators. That is, authors and publishers, after our training, are obviously trying to make textbooks free from discrimination content from the very beginning" [8].

So, in Ukraine, a systematic approach to the anti-discrimination examination is applied, all education stakeholders are involved – both the ministry, international organizations, civil society, authors of textbooks and publishing companies. We have not been able to find similar experiences in other countries.

3. The purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the study is to characterize the expected positive changes in the labor migration of the rural population of Ukraine as a result of the implementation of a comprehensive long-term educational program to create an anti-discrimination environment at the level of a separate rural educational establishment and of a whole village (on the example of the village of Ohijivka).

To achieve this goal, we must accomplish such tasks as:

1. To analyze the experience of the experimental work of the Ohijivka Educational Complex of the

Sakhnovshchyna district of the Kharkiv region on the organization of continuous education of teachers and students on the basis of the non-discriminatory approach in education.

2. To reveal the main directions of work of the anti-discrimination center of the Ohijivka Educational Complex in the context of raising the awareness of educators, student youth and the local population.

3. To consider education as an important factor in preventing rural migrant labor migration and to examine its impact on living conditions, aspirations and opportunities of the rural youth.

4. Materials and methods of research

During the implementation of the complex program, a set of methods was used: theoretical (analysis, modeling, forecasting), empirical (diagnostic, sociometric methods, a method of comparative analysis; a method of pedagogical observation).

The research was conducted on the material of a sociological survey of students of grades 9–11 of the Ohijivka Educational Complex: all 12 (out of 15 according to the lists) present persons were interviewed on the day of the interview in a semi-standardized form.

The components of the educational environment of the Ohijivka Educational Complex, that comprises 100 students and 25 teachers, including administration members, as well as the materials of the anti-discrimination center of the complex, became the materials of the study.

5. Results and discussion

Today, the school must educate children with an active civic position, who act in accordance with moral and ethical principles and are able to make responsible decisions, respect dignity, and human rights, and able to compete in the labor market [9]. But the New Ukrainian School cannot work without a new teacher, whose basic features are openness to change, ability and willingness to learn, to perceive new things, to revise their knowledge and beliefs, and update them. Only people, who are capable of learning throughout life, can teach others to do this.

For example, pedagogical workers of the Ohijivka Educational Complex voluntarily joined the experimental project of the regional level "Scientific and methodological foundations of implementing gender approaches in the system of work of educational institutions for 2014–2018". The project was initiated by the KRONA Gender Information and Analysis Center and Kharkiv Academy of Continuing Education. The participation in this project was the boost for further educators' self-development and change of the educational environment for the non-discriminatory one [10].

At present, an anti-discrimination center has been set up at the Ohijivka Educational Complex. It operates on the basis and in accordance with the current legislation, namely the Constitution of Ukraine, the Law of Ukraine On Education, the Law of Ukraine On the Principles of Prevention and Combating Discrimination, the Law of Ukraine On Ensuring Equal Rights and Opportu-

nities for Women and Men, Presidential Decree Ukraine On Approval of the National Strategy on Human Rights and others.

The work of the Anti-Discrimination Center is carried out according to the plan in the following main directions.

1. Conducting outreach informational and educational workouts and training for pedagogical and scientific-pedagogical employees, students, parents and carers, who replace them, (or for those with whom children live) in order to increase their ability to notice discrimination. For training they use the materials, posted on the websites of the KRONA Gender Information and Analytical Center [11], the Center for Gender Culture, [12], Gender in Detail [13], and such online courses as Non-Discriminatory Approach to Learning [14] and Women and Men: Gender for Everyone [15] and others.

The counseling, provided by the Anti-Discrimination Center, helps pedagogical workers not only get rid of their stereotypes, overcome the difficulties of taking a non-discriminatory approach in education, but also use their obtained knowledge in practice.

2. The anti-discrimination component as part of all sections of the annual work plan. For example, one of the activities, designed in the work plan, is conducting the Global Dignity Day. Some basic principles of this social project are as follows: Everyone has the right to a decent life. A decent life means an opportunity to reach one's potential, which must be supported by decent medical care, education, earnings and a sense of security [16].

An analysis of vocational guidance, taking into account the anti-discrimination approach, indicates a positive shift in the destruction of stereotypes among students. Fig. 1 presents an annual analysis of the number (in percent) of boys, who chose a 'male', 'female', 'neutral' profession and, accordingly, girls who chose a 'male', 'female', 'neutral' profession. In 2014, before the participation of the educational institution in the experimental project of the regional level "Scientific and methodological foundations of the implementation of gender approaches in the system of work of educational institutions for 2014–2018"), choosing a school for further study the students considered what profession they wanted to obtain – a 'female' or 'male' one. The boys mastered the professions, related to law, economics, mechanics, car repair, construction, and girls preferred the service sphere and the humanities. In the chart, we can see that every year the girls and boys' approach to choosing the future careers changed, they got rid of their own stereotypes and chose a profession that they liked and in which they could express their personalities and realize themselves. For example, the girls began to choose computer science, cybernetics, business, law, police, and boys – neutral spheres (medical, pedagogical, earth sciences). Therefore, educational activities and anti-discrimination environment contribute to the development of both critical thinking and balanced career guidance.

Fig. 1. Employment of school leavers

3. The methodological support of lessons and educational activities using a non-discriminatory approach. Teachers should avoid broadcasting their own stereotypes during training sessions; respond equally to mistakes, made by boys and girls; refer to each of them with the same frequency and in the same way (for example, only calling them out by first names and with the same intonation, facial expressions); not to divide children, for example, into groups, by gender; not to divide subjects into 'male' and 'female' ones; to develop tasks of equal complexity for boys and girls.

There is also an optional practice of attending lessons and carrying out their gender examination (for example, counting how many times per lesson a teacher calls out boys and girls to respond from their place and at the board; whether a teacher responds to the raised arm of a child; how many times s/he appeals to boys and how many times – to girls; how many times s/he responds to their shouts positively or negatively). The results are analyzed, discussed and summarized.

Developing celebration concepts and scenarios that take into account the individuality of each child to reveal and enhance their interests, and talents, is one more way to introduce the non-discrimination approach. That is why it is important to analyze all the scenarios of educational and extra-class activities and carefully select materials and refuse to hold holidays and different celebrations under scenarios, containing direct and/or hidden discrimination and stereotypes. For example, to celebrate March 8, children search for information about the history of the holiday; who, why and with what slogans goes to the demonstration on this day; students watch and discuss films (about discrimination, behavior patterns, opportunities to choose their desired profession independently and, as a result, to build their lives not by the 'gender scenario' but by vocation).

4. Audit and monitoring of the space of the educational institution. It is about the placement of visuals

that do not transmit gender stereotypes and do not contain direct and/or hidden discrimination in lobbies, corridors, classrooms, libraries. For example, in the corridors of the Ohijivka Educational Complex, there are such gender-sensitive visuals, developed by the KRONA Gender Information and Analysis Center as: "Modern Steps of Education towards Gender Equality", "Space Free from Discrimination", "I can Choose", a series of 10 illustrations on the topic "Professions/Jobs" [17]. A gender audit was conducted using a specially designed methodology to analyze the extent, to which the principles of gender equality are reflected in the activities of the educational institution and how the gender components are integrated into the educational process and relationships within the staff and students groups, and provide specific recommendations for improvement.

5. Analysis of communication between teachers and students in order to eradicate any manifestation of discrimination. In particular, the school practices the use of the gender-sensitive language, which is to use femininities ('female' words) in speech and written texts (individually or in conjunction with 'masculinities') to name female persons. For example учні/учениці (Ukrainian), вчитель/вчителька (Ukrainian), etc. The doorplates were changed as директор to директорка, секретар to секретарка.

6. Educators share their experiences in creating a non-discriminatory environment at EdCamp Ukraine International Teacher (Un)conferences: "A Gender Breakthrough is Possible: From the Experience of My School" (EdCamp Ukraine 2016) and "Anti-Discriminatory Textbook Examination: Everything You Need to Know" [18].

Within the framework of the *Gender Educational Experiment*, 5 teachers of the Ohijivka Educational Complex participated in a two-day training on developing the anti-discrimination expertise of school textbooks. The anti-discrimination textbook examination aims to

find manifestations of discrimination on protected grounds (race, color, political, religious and other beliefs, gender, age, ability and disability, social background, language, etc.) in the form of stereotypes, xenophobia, ageism, andro- and ethnocentrism, sexism, etc. in textual and non-textual (illustrations, terminology, guidance vocabulary) materials of a textbook and to provide recommendations for their elimination.

Two teachers of the school under discussion are certified national experts in the anti-discrimination analysis of an educational content. Since 2017, they have been conducting an anti-discrimination analysis of electronic versions of textbooks, supposed to be published at the state expense. These teachers have successfully completed the Certification Program for the Preparation of the Expert Circle for the Anti-discrimination Examination of Educational Content (102 hours), on the basis of which they were awarded certificates of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine. In addition, they have passed the certification program "Training for trainers on antidiscrimination examination of educational content" (270 hrs, 9 ECTS credits, 8 modules) and have participated in the development and holding of a training session of the 2nd (advanced) level of expert training and anti-discrimination examination of an educational content to enforce the orders of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine #1190, dated 01/11/2018 and #1191, dated 01/11/2018.

Thus, the educators have not only received the informal education but also have made a significant contribution to the field of non-discrimination in education, initiating, in particular, the activities of the anti-discrimination center by joining the development and

testing of tools of the anti-discrimination approach in education; having made a significant scientific and methodological step and sharing their knowledge in their home region.

Today, the local school has become one of the influential factors in the development of the Ohijivka community. The educational establishment employees, by their own example and through the campaigning work, are not only implementing the non-discriminatory approach, but also enhancing the environmental culture of the villagers. After all, they launched the regional project "Sort the Garbage Out – You'll Live a Happy Life". The aim of the project is to encourage villagers to sort out litter (waste pens, batteries, paper, cellophane balls, plastic bottles and lids, glass are collected) [19]. Now, to make the environment clean and safe for life, every not indifferent and conscious resident annually cleans the village, dams as well as beaches. The entire community has begun to tidy up the park area, have already removed the dry trees, put up benches, fixed broken flower beds, planned to make a playground and lighting. Garbage has also been collected around the well that will be restored in the summer.

The positive initiatives of the Ohijivka community, started by teachers and students of the local school, are described in numerous media reports [20, 21]. Thanks to the initiatives of the school, the population of Ohijivka becomes more socially active, consciously joining its community development. Local people are beginning to understand that the well-being, the implementation of democratic values, are largely dependent on themselves. In recent years, there has been a slight increase in the working-age population (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Population of Ohijivka

Not only former school leavers, who have recently graduated from various higher educational institutions, but also families with children who have lived and worked for more than 10 years in the regional and district

centers of Ukraine are returning to the village. Several families moved to a permanent residence from neighboring villages, as they believe that the Ohijivka Educational Complex provides better services in the education and

upbringing of their children, and the living conditions in the village are more comfortable and modern.

So, we see that quite different at first glance institutions, situations, and people are actually very interconnected and have a great influence on each other. Thus, teachers who are constantly studying, gradually affect the consciousness of the local population, fellow-residents also begin to create something new and useful for the community, i.e. to be socially active. This in turn, improves their living conditions and enhances their desire to stay in their native village.

6. Conclusions

1. Due to the organization of continuous education of teachers, students of the Ohijivka Educational Complex, as well as their relatives, and other local residents on the basis of the non-discriminatory approach, the local school has become one of the influential factors of development of the Ohijivka community through the introduction of the non-discrimination approach into the educational and training process on the principles of equality, enhancement of the ecological culture of the villagers, creation of comfortable living conditions for all residents.

2. Teachers of the Ohijivka Educational Complex joined the experimental project of the regional level "Scientific and methodological foundations of implementing gender approaches in the system of work of educational institutions for 2014 – 2018", launched by the KRONA Gender Information and Analytical Center and Kharkiv Academy of Continuing Education and organized an anti-discrimination center in their school to raise the awareness of educators, students and, the local population. The main directions of the work of the anti-discrimination center of the Ohijivka Educational Complex in the context are as follows: carrying out the informative and educational work, workouts, trainings for teachers, students and parents; introduction of the anti-discrimination component in all sections of an annual curriculum; methodological support of lessons and edu-

cational activities, mutual attendance of lessons and their gender-based examination; placement of gender-sensitive visuals in the educational environment; analysis of communication between teachers and pupils with a view to eradicating any discrimination; development of conceptions of celebrations and scenarios that take into account the individuality of each child, reveal and enhance their interests, talents, organization of holidays, meetings, social events for all residents to disseminate progressive ideas in the society.

3. It has been established, that education is an important factor in preventing labor migration of rural populations through the formation of favorable living conditions, mutual respect, the expansion of ideas about their own opportunities, etc. Only the space, free from discrimination, provides a deconstruction of discriminatory stereotypes in all participants of the educational process, stimulates the development of critical thinking, the formation of democratic values and increase of legal literacy, promotes the prudent and productive vocational guidance of young people, enhancing the motivation of young people to the creative and innovative activity, increases the competitiveness of both individuals and educational institutions as a whole, promotes the anti-discrimination education of parents and the change of the rural environment in general.

The monitoring of the results of the vocational guidance of students, conducted with the anti-discrimination approach in education, indicates a positive shift in the destruction of discriminatory stereotypes, and children begin to understand the positive meaning of their background, to be proud of their own village, trying to make it better. Young people remain in the village where residents promote non-discrimination ideas, sort garbage, arrange eco-friendly rest areas, introduce new information technologies, maintain a cultural center, family reading libraries, a sauna, billiards, a strong football team, organize district beach volleyball competitions and much more.

References

1. Bochkovska A. I., Rudenko L. H. Karty Natsionalnoho atlasu Ukrainy yak informatsiina baza dlia doslidzhennia formuvannia chyselnosti naseleennia. URL: <https://igu.org.ua/uk/node/21095> (Last accessed: 04.02.2020)
2. Derzhavna sluzhba statystyky Ukrainy. Naseleennia. URL: http://www.ukrstat.gov.ua/operativ/operativ2007/ds/nas_rik/nas_u/nas_rik_u.html (Last accessed: 03.02.2020)
3. Kruhlyi stil «Sil'skyi ta ahrarnyi rozvytok: stan ta perspektyvy». URL: <http://www.nas.gov.ua/EN/Messages/Pages/View.aspx?MessageID=5338> (Last accessed: 05.02.2020)
4. Bil'sborrow R. E. Migration, population change, and the rural environment // Environmental change and security program. 2002. Issue 8. P. 69–94. URL: http://legacy.wilsoncenter.org/sites/default/files/Report_8_Bil'sborrow_article.pdf (Last accessed: 06.02.2020)
5. Lucas R. E. B. The effects of proximity and transportation on developing country population migrations // Journal of Economic Geography. 2001. Vol. 1, Issue 3. P. 323–339. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1093/jeg/1.3.323>
6. Mazzucato V. The Study of Transnational Migration: Reflections on a Simultaneous Matched-Sample Methodology // Workshop on Migration and Development Within and Across Borders. New York City, 2005. URL: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/308602073_Operationalising_Transnational_Migrant_Networks_through_a_Simultaneous_Matched_Sample_Methodology (Last accessed: 05.02.2020)
7. Ajaero C. K., Onokala P. C. The Effects of Rural-Urban Migration on Rural Communities of Southeastern Nigeria // International Journal of Population Research. 2013. Vol. 2013. P. 1–10. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1155/2013/610193>
8. Kuklin D. Stereotyp – tse brekhnia pro realnist abo 7 vidpovidei na zapytannia pro antydyskryminatsiinu ekspertyzu shkillykh pidruchnykiv. 2019. URL: https://ukr.lb.ua/society/2019/04/06/423834_stereotip_tse_brehnya_pro.html (Last accessed: 03.02.2020)
9. Pro skhvalennia Kontseptsii realizatsii derzhavnoi polityky u sferi reformuvannia zahalnoi serednoi osvity «Nova Ukrain'ska Shkola» na period do 2029 roku: rozporiadzhennia Kabinetu Ministriv Ukrainy No. 988. 14.12.2016. URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/988-2016-p> (Last accessed: 05.02.2020)

10. Hender v osviti. Pro Ohiivskiy NVK: reportazh kharkivskoho telebachennia. URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2_V0cTQ8z3s (Last accessed: 09.12.2019)
11. Hendernyi informatsiino-analitychnyi tsentr «KRONA». URL: <http://www.krona.org.ua/> (Last accessed: 07.02.2020)
12. Tsentr hendernoi kultury. URL: <https://www.genderculturecentre.org> (Last accessed: 05.02.2020)
13. Hender v detaliakh. URL: <https://genderindetail.org.ua> (Last accessed: 03.02.2020)
14. Nedyskryminatsiyni pidkhdid u navchanni. URL: <https://courses.ed-era.com/courses/course-v1:EdEra-Studena+Inc+1/about> (Last accessed: 05.02.2020)
15. Zhinky ta choloviky: hender dlia vsikh. URL: https://courses.prometheus.org.ua/courses/IRF/101/2015_T2/about (Last accessed: 03.02.2020)
16. Teaching Tools. URL: <https://globaldignity.org/teaching-dignity/teaching-tools/> (Last accessed: 05.02.2020)
17. Hendernochutlyva naochnist dlia shkil ta dytsadkiv. URL: <http://www.krona.org.ua/naochnist.html> (Last accessed: 04.02.2020)
18. EdCamp Ukraine. URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kC92EWUTFxM> (Last accessed: 05.02.2020)
19. Zbyrai rozdilno smittia – bude shchaslyvym zhyttia: shkilne video pro pochatok ekolohichnoho proektu Ohiivskoho navchalno-vykhovnoho kompleksu Sakhnovshchynskoi raionnoi rady Kharkivskoi oblasti. URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cIpEZrb4LEw> (Last accessed: 09.12.2019)
20. Kich T. Ekolohichna problema sela na Kharkivshchyni: do spravy vzialysia dity // Slobidskyi krai. 2017. URL: https://www.slk.kh.ua/news/oblast-online/diti-pridumali_-yak-virishiti-ekologichnu-problemu-sela-na-kharkivshchyni.html (Last accessed: 08.12.2019)
21. Kich T. Dity vykhovuiut doroslykh // Slobidskyi krai. 2017. URL: <https://www.slk.kh.ua/amp/news/suspilstvo/smittyafeniks-yak-pozbutysya-ekologichnoyi-zarazi-nazavzhd-.html> (Last accessed: 08.12.2019)

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